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SCHOOL CAMPAIGNS IN NIGERIA TO PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE AND OCEAN LITERACY

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The children and youth are the future of sustainable aquaculture and the ocean, in ASTRAL we recognise this hence an education campaign within the ASTRAL project is being developed and targeted at primary and secondary school students in Nigeria. This campaign aims to gather the importance of safe and nutritious aquaculture seafood also addressing climate change resilience and ocean influence. The campaign involves several schools across 3 states namely Lagos, Ogun and Oyo reaching a total of 450 students.

ASTRAL (All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture) is a Horizon 2020 project with the objective to promote Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) farming system while increasing social awareness towards the consumption of sustainably produced seafood across the Atlantic countries. To target the young generation, the ASTRAL school campaign among other objectives aims at creating awareness and increase the knowledge base of children and youth on the following: the importance of safe and nutritious aquaculture seafood, IMTA, the benefit of the Atlantic Ocean and the Blue Economy, Climate change mitigation and resilience, ocean influence, aquatic pollution as well as the role and responsibility of the young generation on Ocean protection.

To achieve the ASTRAL goals, the objectives were communicated to different primary and secondary school teachers and students. These schools were adopted as ASTRAL schools forming ASTRAL School Clubs to make learning fun outside the regular curriculum objective of human capital development of the project. Some of the activities of these clubs are Do-it-yourself activities such as setting up small fish farms in the school and their homes(aquariums), creative drawing and video images, telling stories and essay writing on the subject matters. Other activities include educating on waste management (talks on pollution), awareness on recycling and upcycling (developing products from waste) and organizing clean-ups in schools, streets, parks and beaches.

There has been visitation by these schools on excursions to tour aquaculture farms and IMTA models in NIOMR. Researchers are also saddled with the responsibility of engaging these students in their schools.

ASTRAL Schools Clubs participated in the Children Day's 2022 Symposium at NIOMR. With 85 students and 21 teachers from 7 schools within Lagos metropolitan. There were talks from researchers on nutritious aquaculture seafood and the benefits, of care for the ocean.

The impact evaluation of these activities will be done through a competition among the schools on different occasions to achieve the ASTRAL aim. Further information on ASTRAL project can be found at www.astral-project.eu/

Figure 1. Schools on excursions to NIOMR to experience a practical view of various aspects of aquaculture production, the blue economy, climate change and ocean influence.

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Figure 2. NIOMR researchers at ASTRAL School club for its activities in Oyo state to the left, and Badagry, Lagos state to the right.

Figure 3. School Clubs participation in Children Day's 2022 Symposium at NIOMR.

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